

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5041103>

УДК 378.147

ДИСТАНЦИОННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ НА ВОЛНЕ ПАНДЕМИИ

С.М. Левин,

проф. кафедры автоматизированных систем управления,
ТУСУР,
г. Томск

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы дистанционного образования, выявленные при массовом переходе к данной форме обучения в период пандемии COVID-19, происшедшем на фоне продолжающейся реформы высшего образования. Актуальность исследований в этой области обусловлена стремительным ростом популярности дистанционных образовательных программ в период до пандемии, а также предполагаемом последующем увеличении рынка дистанционных образовательных услуг по окончании периода обязательного удалённого обучения. Целью исследования является выявление проблемных аспектов и поиск решений для реализации дистанционного обучения на основе современных педагогических концепций. В процессе исследований выявлены такие проблемы как низкая познавательная самостоятельность студентов, слабая мотивация преподавателей в части эффективной педагогической деятельности, слабая профессиональная подготовка обучающихся в области применения современных педагогических технологий и инструментов электронных образовательных систем. Результаты работы отражены в конкретных рекомендациях, применение которых находится в поле компетенций университетов.

Ключевые слова: дистанционное обучение, студентоцентрированное образование, современные педагогические технологии, лично-ориентированное обучение, реформа образования

DISTANCE LEARNING ON THE PANDEMIC WAVE

S.M. Levin,

Professor of Automated control systems Chair,
TUSUR,
Tomsk

Annotation: The article explores the problems of distance learning classified during the massive transition to this form of education during the COVID-19 pandemic, which occurred against the ongoing reform of higher education. The relevance of research in this area is due to the rapid growth in the popularity of distance learning programs in the period before the pandemic and the expected subsequent increase in the market for distance education services after the end of the mandatory distance learning period. The research aims to identify problematic aspects and find solutions for the implementation of online learning based on modern pedagogical concepts. The research process found such problems as low cognitive independence of students, weak motivation of teachers in effective pedagogical activity, inadequate professional training of teachers in using modern pedagogical technologies and electronic educational tools. The work results reflected in specific recommendations, which are in the field of competence of universities.

Keywords: distance learning, student-centred education, modern pedagogical technologies, student-focused learning, educational reform

When describing the past 2020, we often use such epithets as "unprecedented", "unprecedented", "record", and the like. This is not related to any particular aspect of our daily life, and we are talking about a variety of events that have affected almost all population of the planet during the COVID-19 pandemic – unprecedented administrative restrictions, the transfer of everyday activity to the virtual space in a short time, unprecedented spasmodic growth of distance learning. Such changes have revealed many weaknesses and the unpreparedness of established structures for abrupt changes in external conditions or functional forms. Education achieved through the electronic learning environment was optional until the beginning of last year. The reasons to choose it could be different, but it was never offered as the only acceptable form. The wave of the coronavirus spread has caused the next wave-rapid educational process transfer to a distant format. At the end of February 2020, about 170 million Chinese students began to study at home, and then their number began to increase by the students from European countries. In mid-March, all schools of the Russian Federation switched to distance learning, following the recommendations of the Ministry of Education. By the end of October 2020, 152 Russian universities out of 724 turned to a remote learning format; the rest worked in a mixed format [1]. Thus, by the end of March, more than 1.5 billion students, or 87 % of students in 165 countries worldwide, suffered from school closures [2].

The difficulties of temporarily leaving the classrooms of educational institutions were of a different type and degree of intensity, depending on each country's education system. In those where distance learning was a well-

established element of the educational environment, and pedagogical technologies were adapted for the online format, replacing the blackboard with a computer monitor was almost painless. In others, the introduction of electronic teaching tools revealed the unwillingness of universities and teaching personnel to adapt the educational process to new conditions of existence. If in Russia, as of the end of 2018, the share of online education programs was 1.1 % of the total market of educational services, then in Japan, the United States, and some European countries, it was 20-30 % [3]. Also, we should keep in mind that the culture of this educational model has formed for more than one decade. Isaac Pitman modelled the process of distance education with teacher-student feedback in the middle of the 19th century. The video broadcasting technologies of educational courses and software already used at the beginning of the second half of the 20th century by Houston and Alberta universities. The Southeastern University (USA) in 1985 offered accredited diplomas obtained online. On the other hand, the Russian history of distance education dates back to 1997, when the Ministry of Education of Russia issued Order No. 1050, which allowed experiments in online learning [4].

Let us also note the difference in the educational systems of different states. The Bologna Declaration, signed more than 20 years ago, marked the beginning of a large-scale and profound reforming higher education in Europe [5]. Currently, 48 countries, including the Russian Federation, are participants in the Bologna Process. However, equal participation does not mean identical starting conditions. The reform of higher education in western Europe is a logical continuation of the school reform that began much earlier. In Russian realities, changes in university education coexist with the heritage of conservative school education. As a result, we can note the low independent cognition of students as a product of school learning [6]. This phenomenon complicates the task of universities in the implementation of modern educational standards, complementing it with the need to compensate for the shortcomings of school education with various pedagogical technologies.

Universities without a school heritage are under challenging conditions, should be noted. The teaching team did not spare the negative consequences of the implementation of the reform. Increased reporting requirements accompanying the changes have led to an increase in the role of bureaucracy in higher education institutions [7] – teachers forced to issue countless documents in their daily activities, reducing the degree of attention to the primary function's activities. In addition, the race to improve the university's ranking and implement the principles of the Bologna process focused the attention of the teaching personnel on research work. Pedagogical component sometimes implemented according to the residual principle. As a result, the university fails to compensate for the shortcomings of school education, creating conditions for student-centred learning and

implementing it in practice, which increases the gap between the final skills of students and the requirements of the labour market for the specialist qualifications. Another consequence of this pedagogical work deformation is the slow integration of pedagogical methods into the educational process has to provide student-centred learning.

Transition to online learning should not be considered as modelling on the LMS (Learning Management System) platform of the educational process taking place in university classrooms. The difference in the conditions in which students find themselves in both cases excludes the effectiveness of this modelling. The task of online education is the practical adaptation of education when changing the form of education. However, not all universities adhered to this position in 2020. Spontaneous changes associated with imperative administrative constraints did not always provide an opportunity for fully informed decisions.

Indeed, one cannot put an equal sign between full-time and distant forms. One should not expect a sudden miracle from LMS either, and their constituent elements are only pedagogical tools [8, 9], sometimes very productive, but they cannot replace teachers. Compiling the educational process using distance learning technologies, the formation of the course, filling it with educational elements, and finally implementing the learning process is the teacher's task. The use of modern pedagogical methods follows the principle of creating conditions for students to construct their knowledge instead of transferring ready-made information to students. At the same time, a student-centred learning method should become the central element of most pedagogical technologies scenarios. Its main elements are activities comprehension, setting a personal goal, an activity plan, implementing the plan, reflection, assessment, goals adjustment or redefinition – the core around which built up the curriculum content [10].

With the distant educational form, a large load should fall on asynchronous elements. Edgar Dale's cone, modified by his followers, testifies to the low lectures efficiency at their high abstraction level [11]. Presentations accompanying webinars increase the level of material perception, however, the volume memorized data indicator remains within 30 % of the stated. More effective are specific action observation, participation in a discussion and real project imitation. It necessitates the inclusion of critical thinking technology, cases, cooperation technology, etc., in the educational process.

Unfortunately, the investigation of education courses of several Russian universities LMS, and not only, has shown that these learning management platforms contain courses with a very insufficient set of methods and supporting elements. There are webinars offered for students, self-study teaching materials, and traditional individual tasks far from practice cases. It can also be concluded from this that not all teachers strive to comprehend the LMS elements. However, online education using one or another pedagogical technology required a qualified

acquaintance with the educational platform resources [12]. In cases where a teacher practices two or three learning elements within the education course framework, the productivity of such training significantly reduced.

Research about distance learning usage in Russian higher education institutions has revealed some problems. First of all, the low cognitive independence of students, then – the unpreparedness and weak motivation of the teaching staff. It should also be noted that teachers are insufficiently qualified when using LMS in the educational process.

With a conscious approach to teaching students, such problems can be solved by universities' efforts.

First of all, to improve students' cognitive independence, using relevant pedagogical methods in education courses in the studied disciplines: cooperation technologies, group learning, peer-2-peer pairs, including relevant forms of knowledge control. Transition to the learning paradigm and modern pedagogical methods creates required conditions forcing students to independent activity.

Of course, student readiness alone is not enough to get the wanted result. The teacher's active participation is a prominent and integral success factor. Rebuilding the teacher's motivation system could make it effective. A pedagogical component should be significant both in volume and content. Without such changes to transform the educational process and update the methods used, the reforming burden and developing various forms of education will fall on a few enthusiasts shoulders who value the university's honour and national higher education more than their wallet.

It is also necessary to ensure the possibility to teach professors to use the electronic educational systems tools, adding this with a relevant position in the motivation system. LMS operated by universities cannot be training grounds for teachers, while they expected to have a professional skill level in the complete range of electronic instruments.

In six months or a year, the pandemic will become history. Nonetheless, the world will not return to the indicators of the previous period, when the online education percentage in the general market of educational services in some countries barely exceeded 1 % [3]. The financial attractiveness of this educational form is too big. Moreover, it ensures the implementation of the education accessibility principle in the literal sense of the word. The distance learning potential is evident. There is only one but a big and important step left to take – to provide online education with the required quality. It depends on whether such a form in Russia will become a dead-end for pedagogical evolution or a promising opportunity for development.

Список литературы

- [1] Исакова А.И. Платформы взаимодействия со студентами в условиях пандемии COVID-19 и дистанционного обучения. / А.И. Исакова, А.М. Кориков, С.М. Левин. // Современное образование: повышение конкурентоспособности университетов: В 2 ч. Ч. 2: материалы международной научно-методической конференции, 28-29 января 2021 г., Томск, Россия. – Томск: Изд-во Томск. гос. ун-та систем упр. и радиоэлектроники, 2021. 189-195 с.
- [2] UNESCO, UNESCO rallies international organizations, civil society and private sector partners in a broad Coalition to ensure #LearningNeverStops [press release]. 26 March 2020. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <https://en.unesco.org/news/unesco-rallies-international-organizations-civil-society-and-private-sector-partners-broad>. (дата обращения: 12.05.2021).
- [3] Российский рынок дистанционного обучения: итоги 2018 г., прогноз до 2021 г. – М.: NeoAnalyticsю. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://www.neoanalytics.ru/pages/rossiiskii-gynok-distancionnogo-obucheniya-2019/>. (дата обращения: 25.04.2021).
- [4] Министерство общего и профессионального образования Российской Федерации. Приказ от 30.05.1997 г. № 1050 «О проведении эксперимента в области дистанционного образования».
- [5] The Bologna process and the search for excellence: between rhetoric and reality, the emotional reactions of teachers. / I.P. Freire, M.T. Estrela, A. Amaral, J.A.E. Santo. // Teaching in Higher Education. – 2017. Vol. 22. Issue 4. 467-482 p.
- [6] Иванова М.А. Болонский процесс и самостоятельность студентов: российская специфика. / М.А. Иванова. // Высшее образование в России. – 2018. Т. 27. № 3. 48-58 с.
- [7] Байденко В.И. Нынешний раунд Болонского процесса: сохранение оптимизма. И немного о российском (Статья 1). / В.И. Байденко, Н.А. Селезнева. // Высшее образование в России. – 2017. № 10. 94-108 с.
- [8] Левин С.М. Не все LMS одинаково полезны [для обучения]. / С.М. Левин. // Национальная ассоциация ученых. – 2021. Т.3. № 66. 22-26 с.
- [9] Bhattacharyya A.R. Do learning management systems really manage learning? // Report. The University of Texas at Austin. – 2020. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/10932>. (дата обращения: 10.05.2021).
- [10] Краевский В.В. Принципы личностно-ориентированного обучения. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://www.elitarium.ru/princip-obuchenie>

poznanie-celi-znaniya-organizacija-soderzhanie-obrazovaniya. (дата обращения: 11.05.2021).

[11] Lee S.J. Edgar Dale: A significant contributor to the field of educational technology. / S.J. Lee, T.C. Reeves. // Educational Technology. – 2007. Vol.47. No. 6. 56-59 p.

[12] Noreen S. Implementation of learning management system: A way ahead on the digital journey in distance learning. / S. Noreen. // Open Praxis. – 2020. Vol. 12. 329-342 p.

Bibliography (Transliterated)

[1] Isakova A.I. Platforms for interaction with students in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and distance learning. / A.I. Isakova, A.M. Korikov, S.M. Levin. // Modern education: increasing the competitiveness of universities: At 2 hours, Part 2: materials of the international scientific and methodological conference, January 28-29, 2021, Tomsk, Russia. – Tomsk: Publishing house Tomsk. state un-that of control systems. and radio electronics, 2021.189-195 p.

[2] UNESCO, UNESCO rallies international organizations, civil society and private sector partners in a broad Coalition to ensure #LearningNeverStops [press release]. 26 March 2020. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://en.unesco.org/news/unesco-rallies-international-organizations-civil-society-and-private-sector-partners-broad>. (date of access: 12.05.2021).

[3] Russian distance learning market: results of 2018, forecast until 2021 – M.: NeoAnalyticsy [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://www.neoanalytics.ru/pages/rossiiskii-rynok-distancionnogo-obucheniya-2019/>. (date of access: 25.04.2021).

[4] Ministry of General and Professional Education of the Russian Federation. Order of 30.05.1997, No. 1050 "On conducting an experiment in the field of distance education".

[5] The Bologna process and the search for excellence: between rhetoric and reality, the emotional reactions of teachers. / I.P. Freire, M.T. Estrela, A. Amaral, J.A.E. Santo. // Teaching in Higher Education. – 2017. Vol. 22. Issue 4. 467-482 p.

[6] Ivanova M.A. The Bologna Process and Student Independence: Russian Specificity. / M.A. Ivanova. // Higher education in Russia. – 2018. Vol. 27. No. 3. 48-58 p.

[7] Baydenko V.I. The current round of the Bologna Process: maintaining optimism. And a little about Russian (Article 1). / V.I. Baidenko, N.A. Seleznev. // Higher education in Russia. – 2017. No. 10. 94-108 p.

[8] Levin S.M. Not all LMSs are equally useful [for training]. / S.M. Levin. // National Association of Scientists. – 2021. Vol. 3. No. 66. 22-26 p.

[9] Bhattacharyya A.R. Do learning management systems really manage learning? // Report. The University of Texas at Austin. – 2020. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/10932>. (date of access: 10.05.2021).

[10] Kraevsky V.V. The principles of student-centered learning. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://www.elitarium.ru/princip-obuchenie-poznanie-celiznaniya-organizacija-soderzhanie-obrazovanija>. (date of access: 11.05.2021).

[11] Lee S.J. Edgar Dale: A significant contributor to the field of educational technology. / S.J. Lee, T.C. Reeves. // Educational Technology. – 2007. Vol. 47. No. 6. 56-59 p.

[12] Noreen S. Implementation of learning management system: A way ahead on the digital journey in distance learning. / S. Noreen. // Open Praxis. – 2020. Vol.12. 329-342 p.

© С.М. Левин, 2021

Поступила в редакцию 02.05.2021

Принята к публикации 15.05.2021

Для цитирования:

Левин С.М. Дистанционное обучение на волне пандемии // Инновационные научные исследования : сетевой журнал. 2021. № 5-2(7). С. 243-250. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>